

“Meaning” in Mentality: Stray thoughts on memory

Gerard Marx* Chaim Gilon

¹MX Biotech Ltd., Jerusalem, Israel.

²Institute of Chemistry, Hebrew University, Jerusalem, Israel.

Correspondence: Gerard Marx
MX Biotech Ltd, Jerusalem, Israel.

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Abstract

Mentality and consciousness arise from complex physiological processes in the brain, yet their underlying mechanisms remain poorly understood. This study aims to identify the cellular and molecular processes responsible for generating mental states, with a particular focus on memory as a measurable parameter of mentality.

Biological memory can be quantified in terms of retention time; however, a comprehensive understanding requires identification of the cellular processors and biochemical mechanisms involved. In this context, we propose a tripartite mechanism linking physiological responses to stimuli with the biochemical encoding of emotive states as memory.

This model highlights the coordinated roles of neurons, the neural extracellular matrix (nECM/PNN), and astrocyte clusters in encoding, storing, and interpreting cognitive information. We propose that “meaning” emerges from the recognition of stored memory patterns processed by astrocyte networks, which interact closely with neural circuits responsible for sensory input and motor output.

This conceptual framework provides a biochemical perspective on cognition and offers a potential pathway toward understanding the molecular basis of consciousness.

Keywords: Memory, tripartite mechanism, signaling, transmitters, emotions, neuron, astrocyte, mental.

Background

Meaning relates to mentality, which emerges from the physiologic reactions of brain cells that transform physical sensations into a mental experience. However, mentality is neither force, nor mass, nor speed, nor spin, nor light, nor binary code. None of these physics parameters provide a concept that envelops the enigma of mentality (1-12). Clearly, a new paradigm is needed to conceptualize the experiential states that emerge from the biochemical workings of brain cells. One really has to think “outside the box”.

What is mentality?

Ignorance of the mechanism of humanity's most intimate experience is reflected by historical turns to astrology or religion. Today, many look to computer information theory or quantum mechanics to comprehend mentality (1-12).

Some researchers look to mapping anatomical connections within the brain to provide insights into the unique processing talent of the brain. Some track this talent through the evolution of brains from fruit flies to mouse to human. They hope that evolutionary tracking can provide a key clue towards a "generative computational brain model" (11, 12). However, combined topological and spatial modeling of the brain overlooks the molecular features that underlie the evolution of all organs. In particular, it does not address how the brain processes cognitive information to generate persistent memory.

Most cited works focus only on neurons as cellular processors. They generally ignore glial cells (astrocytes) as having any bearing on the brain's processing powers. Notwithstanding, a number of experimental findings identify astrocytes as cellular instigators of mental talents (15-28).

Phase Changes

Physics provides a few examples of phase changes of one type of energy into another aspect (13, 14) (Figures 1, 2). The generation of mentality suggests a phase change, a transcendence of caloric energy into mental states, but we have no physical metric to grasp its essence. The equations of thermodynamics are mum regarding the transcendence of caloric energy into mental states. Possibly, analogy to other phenomena that involve phase change of energy can provide a clue. For example, the generation of laser light by electrical stimulation of a diode (12). Or the generation of electrical current by exposure to light (photo-electric effect) (Figures 1, 2). We understand the conversion of sunlight into caloric energy (photosynthesis). Here, we can monitor the transformation of caloric energy into physicality and metabolic processes, but are stumped by its generation of mental states (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Laser: Light emitted by electrical diode.

Figure 2. Photoelectric: Electron stream emitted by light.

Biology exemplifies another class of energy phase changes, that we experience but struggle to comprehend (Figure 3)

Figure 3; Sunlight instigates photosynthesis which generates caloric energy which is manifest biologically by physical effort and mysteriously transcends into mental states.

Emotions and Memory

The realm of mentality is not described by length, mass or time. Rather, a mental state emerges from the complex interactions of brain cells in the "brain space". Our goal is to identify the cellular and molecular processes that generate mental states. We focus on brain memory,

Brain Cells

Brain cells are primarily comprised of:

a. Neurons

Synaptic neural circuits that conduct sensory signals (cognitive information, cog-info) from the body, transmitting them electrochemically to the brain. Neurons "write" this cognitive information into the neural extracellular matrix (nECM/PNN) as memory, with the involvement of trace metals and neurotransmitters (NTs), as described in the tripartite mechanism.

b. Astrocytes

Astrocytes "read" the information stored within the nECM/PNN through chemographic processes and interpret this input as experience and memory.

Evidence indicates that astrocytes, are involved in all facets of cognitive processes.

Anatomical studies show that human astrocytes form innumerable clusters that integrate cognitive information (cog-info) to achieve consciousness. These cells are crucial for cognitive functions, including learning

as a testable parameter of mentality. This is convenient as we already have knowledge of computer memory.

Our series of essays (29-36) attempts to do this in "bite-size" pieces, with citations of the many experimental works of neuro-biologists and neuro-chemists.

and and explicit memories (14-27).

Clearly, without describing the process of mentation in molecular terms, we will not grasp its essence. Recent experiments describe the critical role of astrocyte ensembles in generating memory recall. We "connect the dots" and conceive that astrocytes are the brain cells that decode the sensory information encoded in the nECM/PNN (memories) and transcend it into consciousness. These cellular components are the drivers of mentality by virtue of their control over the encoding/decoding of cog-info stored within the surrounding nECM/PNN.

"Recognition" involves the recall of processed memory and is the basis of consciousness. Effectively, mentation (conscious thought) is performed by clusters of brain astrocytes. Action required after mentation is chemodynamically processed by astrocytes which instigate the neural circuits, to electrodynamically act on muscles and organs.

Various publications describe the critical role of astrocyte ensembles in generating memory (15-28). In effect, the astrocytes do the processing (remembering and thinking), the neurons function to sense and to activate muscles and glands.

Of course, the neurons and glial cells (astrocytes) are morphologically intimate, so that mentation is entangled

with body responses. Both cell types secrete modulating molecules that affect memory and may be considered as encoders of memory (Tables 1, 2). Any drug or event that decreases the optimal performance of one cell type would negatively impact on the performance of the other. Experimentally or behaviorally, it would be difficult to distinguish.

Table 1. Basic emotions associated with neurotransmitters* and learning/memory.

Emotion	Emotive Neurotransmitter (NT)	Memory function
Anger	Adrenaline, glutamate, serotonin	YES
Anxiety	Dopamine, serotonin	YES
Arousal	Acetylcholine, adrenaline, orexin	YES
Fear	GABA, glutamate, norepinephrine,	YES
Appetite, hunger	Amino acids	YES
Joy/depression	Aspartate, glutamate, norepinephrine, serotonin, insulin	YES
Love, sociability	Dopamine, epinephrine, glutamate, oxytocin, tryptophan, tyrosine, vasopressin,	YES
Pain	Dopamine, GABA, endorphins, glutamate, glycine, histamine, norepinephrine	YES
Sex	Acetylcholine, dopamine, serotonin, prolactin, pheromone, testosterone	YES

*Released by neurons.

Table 2. Gliotransmitters* (GTs) that modulate memory

Emotive Gliotransmitter (GT)	Memory function
Glutamate	YES
D-Serine	YES
GABA,	YES
Cytokines	YES
Cholesterol/apolipoprotein	YES
ATP/ Adenosine	YES

* Released by astrocytes.

Information vs Cognitive Information

A clue as to how memory is embodied in the neural circuitry would go a long way to clarify mental processes. Information (info) and cognitive information (cog-info) are similar in that they both require a physical (i.e. chemical) manifestation (42) as well as an observer to recognize such. Info is binary formatted. By contrast cog-info is experiential but incapable of being detected by computers or perceived by other observers. Cog-info is intimate, subjective and unique to each being.

“Meaning” is inconsequential in a binary or quantal information system. Info is inherently “demotive”. It cannot convey an evaluation of worth. By contrast, the meaning of a cog-info message is inherently emotive. It resides in the mind of the neural creature whose very existence depends on its ability to remember and render a judgement as to the “survival worth” of the message.

According to the laws of quantum mechanics, info can never be destroyed. By contrast, the cog-info of the neural net disappears when the creature dies.

It can only be vaguely resuscitated in the memory of the survivors, the offspring or acquaintances of the deceased.

Discussions of structure and process at the level of mental representation have been problematic for neuroscien-

tists. There is an inescapable need for a representation system, but none has been developed. Codes for synaptic plasticity have been found wanting; action potentials (firing) are too fleeting to enable persistent representation of emotive memory.

Tripartite Mechanism of Neural Memory (29-35)

We aspire to present a single narrative for neural memory woven from the experimentally confirmed components available to the brain cells, namely the nECM/PNN, the trace metals and the NTs/GTs.

Figure 2; Tripartite mechanism of the chemical formation of emotive memory units with typical NTs and GTs of which there are more than 90.

Below (Figure 3), shows single saccharide isomerizations that impact on metal binding encoding options. Consider how coding options are exponentially multiplied in poly-saccharides comprising the nECM/PNN.

Figure 3; Cyclohexyl carbon skeleton illustrates the many isomers available to a saccharide for modulate metal cation binding, each conformational isomer considered as a discrete coding option. Due to their isomeric flexibility, saccharides present exponential binding and coding options.

The tripartite mechanism provides a biochemical description of a mental talent i.e. neural memory. It invokes the hydrogel surrounding the neuron, the “neural extracellular matrix” (nECM/PNN) (36), which functions as a “memory material” to encode and store cognitive units of information (cuinfo). The dopants (>10 neuro-metals, >90 transmitters (GTs and NTs) provide the cells with Avogadro scale ($\text{\AA} = 6 \times 10^{23}$) of “effectors” for encoding emotive cog-info in memory (Figure 2). The tripartite hypothesis does not annul the concept of “synaptic plasticity”. Rather, it provides a detailed account of how such plasticity is rendered operative.

Neural nets are powered by the Life Force of metabolism. Their responses to their environment are inherently emotive, powered by molecular processes involving trace

metals, GTs and NTs, as described by the tripartite mechanism (figure 2), where the memory units (cuinfo) are embellished with GTs and NTs, to elicit and recall emotive states (Figure 2).

A major problem in all published representations of neurons and astrocytes is that they are all shown as if suspended in space (i.e. "naked"). That is far from biologic reality. It is an experimentally verified fact that all these cells are surrounded by a hydrogel termed nECM/PNN which we propose performs as a "memory material".(Figure 4).

Figure 4. Representation of
A. neurons and astrocytes
B. nECM/PNN
C. neurons and astrocytes enmeshed in the nECM/PNN.

Conclusion

“Chemistry is the only physical science that offers a pathway to understanding animate biology.” Medawar, 1967.

The "wedding" of computer processing with brain cell mentation is inadequate. The absence of emotive signifiers in binary computational algorithms reveals a deep lack of biological relevance.

Computer information theory is constituted to be "blind" with regard to emotive content. Thus for biologic relevance, the term "information" needs to be modified to "cognitive information" replete with emotive qualities.

The linkage of morphological changes of neural microstructures to learning and memory, termed "synaptic plasticity" (SP), is rendered operational via the biochemical tripartite mechanism. The syntax of memory is comprised of molecules linked into sets of complexes, These constitute the cog-info which is processed by the astrocyte clusters to be experienced as emotive memory rendered as "meaning".

Many philosophers have attempted to scale the "cliffs of memory" ...Aristotle, Plato, Augustine, Spinoza, Descartes, Bergson to name only a few. But only John Stuart Mill (1806-1873) alluded to "mental chemistry", suggesting that the combination of molecular components generated a mental state. In our time, the linguist Noam Chomsky posited the following (37):

- "Since the subject is a physical organism, the system attributed to it must have finite representations." (p 162)
- "An empirical argument must be brought to bear." (p 177)

Artificial intelligence (AI) founders on the lack of emotions, which provide meaning to cog-info. Failure to provide an atomic scale description of synaptic plasticity as it relates to memory is not a superficial defect that can be remedied by referring to an undefined physical trace of memory (38-41). But until the molecular basis of

memory is clarified, no theory of cognition (42-44) will achieve a satisfactory scientific concept.

The ultimate description of neural memory will only be realized by identifying the cellular processors and the causative chemistry underlying mentality. Until the molecular basis of memory is clarified, no theory of cognition will achieve scientific consensus. In that spirit, we propose a tripartite mechanism that provides linkage between physiologic reactions to stimuli and the biochemical encoding of emotive states manifest as memory. Meaning emerges from the recognition of memory patterns perceived by the clusters of cellular processors, notably the astrocytes in the brain. All this is powered by the Life Force which we experience but don't understand. Of course, the astrocytes are linked with the neuron circuits that input sensory information, and enmeshed with the neuron circuits that instigate body muscles and glands.

We offer the tripartite mechanism of neural memory as a biochemical alternative to the long-standing proposals of philosophers, such as Aristotle who considered thought as arising from "things" (materials); Kant from the structure of Mind; and Wittgenstein as arising from language.

Thus, the caveat impresses:

The brain is much more than a computer

The Life Force powering mentality is beyond our ken.

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